

First Law of Thermodynamics from Mechanics of Photon Absorption in a Moving Frame Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 8, 2024

In Part I, we considered a photon being absorbed by a gas at rest and argued that essentially all of the photon energy, $d\epsilon_0$, is converted into thermal energy because the photon momentum is small compared to the momentum of the system after absorption, i.e. the system hardly moves. We then analyzed the system as seen by someone watching a moving gas and separated the change in energy into an energy change portion involving no change in momentum of the system, $(1-v) g(v) d\epsilon_0$, and another, a change strictly due to a change in momentum, $v g(v) d\epsilon_0$, where $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$.

In this note, we argue that the zero momentum piece should be further decomposed into a heat term and an internal work piece. In other words, $(1-v) g(v) d\epsilon_0$ is not entirely heat. We argue that there are two types of work in the problem: an internal one by the gas associated with a decrease in velocity if momentum is held constant, and an increase in momentum due to the absorption of the photon. These two work pieces cancel, leaving $g(v) d\epsilon_0$ as the increase in energy. This is linked to an increase in internal energy, but is enhanced by $g(v)$ because this internal energy is moving. Thus, there is consistency between what is seen in the lab and moving frames.

This suggests that the definition $1/T = dS/dE$ holding collective parameters constant is more complicated than it appears. In the case of a boost, S is the same in the rest and moving frames, but energy changes. Thus, it seems that one wants an energy change not associated with a collective parameter when calculating temperature. A boost is associated with the collective parameter velocity of the moving system. Such an interpretation leads to the dS/dE as being evaluated in a rest frame with further collective parameters (such as volume) held constant in that frame, we suggest. Even though T is calculated in the rest frame, heat energy receives the usual $g(v)$ factor from a boost.

Heat, Temperature and Internal Work for an Ideal Gas at Rest

Consider an ideal gas in a container at rest. There is a temperature associated with the average kinetic energy of a molecule, i.e.

$$E = 1.5NkT = 1.5nRT \quad ((1))$$

Furthermore there is an internal pressure of the gas $PV=nRT$ balanced by a force from the container.

If the gas absorbs heat (e.g. photons), the temperature increases, but temperature may change even without a change in heat.

In Newtonian mechanics a change in center-of-mass momentum is linked with external work which is directional in space. There is, however, the notion of internal work. For an ideal gas, consider allowing each end of the container to move by $dx/2$ under the action of the gas

pressure, balanced by the wall force. Internal (not external) work occurs because the center-of-mass momentum does not change, and one does not have a specific direction because each wall moves in the opposite direction. There is, however, a collective parameter, namely volume, which measures internal work, as opposed to center-of-mass momentum which measures external work. Thus, the gas pushes the walls causing internal work to occur at the expense of the gas energy:

$$dE = (\text{heat}=0) - d\text{Work} \quad \text{or} \quad 1.5 nR dT = -P dV \quad ((2))$$

In this case, temperature drops due to internal work, but there is no heat flow. We stress that there seems to be a collective parameter (not linked with averaging) which is a signature of work. Here dV is the signature. T is a collective parameter, but it is directly linked with averaging and not with any collective effect acting on all single particles. (This becomes an important point for Lorentz boosts.)

If heat is 0, then for this quasistatic process, $TdS = 0$, or entropy should be constant. Thus, a temperature change does not necessarily indicate a change in entropy.

Using the Sackur-Tetrode entropy expression for an ideal gas (1):

$$dS = d(\ln V) + 3/2 d(\ln T) \quad \text{or} \quad TdS = TdV/V + 1.5 dT \quad ((3))$$

Using $dE = -dW$ yields $1.5 NR dT = -NRT/V dV$ so $dS = 0$ as expected.

We now consider the absorption of a photon by a large gas system.

Absorption of a Photon by a Large Gas System

If one considers the absorption of a photon with energy $h\nu$ by a large gas system at rest, then the momentum of the gas system hardly changes. In other words, the energy of the photon heats the gas because no collective parameter of the gas changes. This should lead to a change in temperature. We note that if one applies a force to the gas system and moves it, collective energy is given to the system, i.e. external work is done, but entropy = $\ln(\text{number of states})$ does not change because one has simply given the system collective energy. We suggest a boost is associated with the collective parameter, center-of-mass v , while volume is a collective parameter linked with a non-center of mass change.

Temperature seems to be linked with partitioning energy among the many particles in such a way as to maximize entropy (\ln of the number of states) without worrying about collective parameters, if possible. For example, if one considers a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas at rest, then volume is a collective parameter, but if it is held constant, it does not affect the partitioning of energy among single particles. This is governed by:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad \text{i.e. the most amount of bias is removed} \quad ((4))$$

Temperature is introduced as a parameter such that: $\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((5)).$

One then fixes temperature by calculating the average energy in the system (which is automatically at rest.) In some cases, as in a Fermi-Dirac or Bose gas, there are scattering biases which one may not remove and these lead to $G(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((6)).

We argue that a boost is linked with a collective parameter v (center-of-mass) and is not a bias which affects entropy, i.e. the partitioning of energy among the single particles.. Thus, the parameter T seems to apply to a scenario in which the collective parameter v does not appear, i.e. to the rest frame of the gas system. The energy of the rest frame, $e(\text{rest})$, then becomes $g(v) e(\text{rest})$ as seen when the gas is moving. In other words, temperature seems to be linked to a calculation of partitioning among single particles which removes as much bias as possible.

In Part I, we considered watching the absorption of a photon of energy dmo in the rest frame ($g(v_1) dmo$ in a frame watching a gas system move at speed v_1 in the x direction). We argued that the change in energy could be broken into two pieces:

$$\text{Change in energy} = dE = g(v_1) (1-v_1) dmo + v_1 g(v_1) dmo \quad ((7))$$

The second term on the RHS side is the change in energy due to external work by the photon in changing the system's momentum. The first term is the change in energy keeping the system's momentum constant. In such a case, there may still be internal work done. We argue that work is linked with changing collective parameters. A change in system momentum is an example of external work based on the collective parameter p (center of mass). If the gas system absorbs energy (i.e. rest mass), then for $dp=0$, one should have a decrease in velocity of the center-of-mass, and this collective parameter change should indicate internal work done. Thus, the first term on the RHS of ((7)) should be a combination of heat and internal work and the second term, external work.

If one wishes the physical description in the rest frame to match that in the frame watching the moving gas, then all of the photon energy should go to heat (not work). Given that this heat is like rest mass and is moving, the overall energy of this heat should be $g(v_1) dmo$. This implies that internal work should be $-v_1 d(v_1) dmo$.

Thus, internal and external work cancel in order that dmo is completely absorbed in the rest frame as heat, but appears as $g(v_1) dmo$ as seen in a frame watching the gas move, i.e. the heat energy moves like rest mass with speed v_1 .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may have both external and internal work and that each is associated with different collective parameters. For example, volume change may describe internal work for a gas. A change in center-of-mass momentum indicates external work, but a change in center-of-mass velocity with momentum held constant may indicate internal work. Thus, we suggest that one must consider all collective parameters (which change) in the system as being linked to work. Temperature on the other hand is a parameter linked with single particle collisions which are arranged to occur with as little bias as possible. Thus, one would not consider changes in p center-of-mass, center-of-mass velocity (with p constant) or even volume

when trying to calculate how energy is distributed among single particles. This suggests that for the case of Lorentz boosts that one considers a rest frame when calculating temperature.

In the case of an absorbed photon, in the rest frame, all of its energy, dmo , is converted essentially into heat energy, i.e. is used in a non-biased manner. One may consider a photon being absorbed by a moving gas. Then, there will be a change in energy due to momentum change (i.e. external work), but what is left (an energy change due to no center-of-mass momentum change) still involves a change in the collective parameter center-of-mass v_1 , suggesting internal work. Thus, we suggest that internal and external work cancel, leaving $g(v_1) dmo$ as the energy absorbed as heat (which still carries motion energy). In order to calculate a temperature change, one needs to go into the rest frame in which the bias of motion v_1 is eliminated. In such a frame, one may maximize entropy. This suggests that one use a thermometer moving with the system so that there is no bias between the thermometer and the gas. (The idea of a moving thermometer has been presented in (2)).

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sackur%E2%80%93Tetrode_equation
2. Gavassino, L. The zeroth law of thermodynamics in special relativity (2020)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2005.06396.pdf>